

Coexistence of Vulvar Crohn's Disease and Hidradenitis Suppurativa: A Diagnostic and Therapeutic Challenge

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Abstract

Vulvar Crohn's disease is a rare condition, reported only in clinical cases; it may complicate luminal involvement of the disease or be its only clinical manifestation. Difficult to diagnose, the most commonly described clinical presentation is edema, deep linear fissures, erythema, and painful labial ulceration. Various treatment protocols have been discussed, but no recommendations have been established. Its association with other skin disorders, such as pyoderma gangrenosum, has been reported, but the association with Verneuil's disease has never been published. We report the case of a 45-year-old woman diagnosed with isolated vulvar Crohn's disease after two years of suffering, associated with axillary hidradenitis suppurativa (HS).

Introduction

Crohn's disease (CD) is a chronic inflammatory disease characterized by extensive digestive damage. Extra-digestive manifestations may complicate or even reveal the disease in 45% of cases [1]. Vulvar skin involvement is rare [2,3], described only in clinical cases, and may coexist with luminal digestive involvement or be the sole clinical manifestation of the disease [4]. Hidradenitis suppurativa (HS) has been defined as a chronic, recurrent, and debilitating inflammatory skin disease, which usually presents after puberty with deep, inflamed, and painful lesions, affecting the body areas with the presence of apocrine glands [5]. The coexistence of vulvar CD and Verneuil's disease is extremely rare, and no cases have ever been published.

We report here the first case of HS associated with isolated vulvar CD without luminal involvement.

Clinical Case

A 45-year-old female patient with a nephew being treated for Crohn's disease of the small intestine underwent surgery for hemorrhoidal pathology in October 2023. On exploration in the operating room, a large fissure was found within a hemorrhoidal pack. Histological examination revealed a hemorrhoidal dystrophy with the presence of a tuberculoid granuloma without caseous necrosis. Anti-bacillary treatment was initiated and continued for 6 months, without any real evidence of tuberculosis. Two years later, the patient consulted a dermatologist for diffuse vulvar lymphedema with multiple fissures and rhagades, as well as progressively worsening fistulizing

More Information

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axillary lesions (Figure 1 and 2). Histological examination of the vulvar lesions revealed non-necrotizing tuberculoid granulomatous inflammation, with no pathogen visualization.

Figure 1. Isolated vulvar Crohn's Disease: Diffuse Vulvar Lymphedema with Multiple Rhagades and Linear Fissures

Figure 2. Hidradenitis Suppurativa (Verneuil's disease): Axillary Fistulizing Lesions Associated with Chronic Inflammatory Changes

The appearance was suggestive of Crohn's disease or tuberculosis. Tissue PCR (Polymerase Chain Reaction) for *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* at this site was negative, as was the QuantiFERON-TB Gold test. As for the axillary lesions, histology showed moderate chronic dermatitis with acute ulceration, with no specificity and no malignancy. The endoscopic work-up, consisting of gastroscopy and colonoscopy, showed no abnormality in favour of Crohn's disease. The fecal Calprotectin level was 10ug/g and the CT-entrogaphy showed no evidence of bowel thickening or active inflammation. The patient's diagnosis was isolated vulvar Crohn's disease without luminal digestive involvement associated with axillary Verneuil's disease. Treatment

consisted of Tetracyclines and intravenous Infliximab (5mg/kg/day) in combination with Azathioprine (1.5mg/kg/day).

Discussion

In 1964 Parks et al. reported the first case of vulvar Crohn's disease [6], and over 50 cases have since been published in the literature [3]. Vulvar involvement in Crohn's disease may result from direct contiguous extension from the gastrointestinal tract, but more commonly occurs as a metastatic manifestation, representing about 91% of reported cases [3,7]. This condition is frequently underdiagnosed due to its rarity and the nonspecific nature of the clinical presentation, which leads to delayed treatment.

Clinically, the lesions most frequently described in the literature are erythema, edema, linear "knife-like" ulcerations of progressive aggravation, and fissures [8]. Ulcerations may evolve into condyloma-like lesions. In addition to pain, patients often report malodorous vaginal discharge and pruritus [9].

The diagnosis of vulvar Crohn's disease is made by histological examination after skin biopsy of vulvar lesions, typically revealing a non-caseating granulomatous inflammation without identifiable pathogens. The initial aim is to rule out other differential diagnoses: tuberculosis, sarcoidosis, lymphogranuloma venereum, pyogenic infections, syphilis, and hidradenitis suppurativa [10]. In our case, the negative tissue PCR and QuantiFERON-TB test, along with the absence of caseous necrosis and persistence of lesions despite anti-tuberculosis treatment, strongly supported the diagnosis of isolated vulvar CD.

The association of vulvar CD with HS is particularly intriguing. Hidradenitis suppurativa, known as acne inversa, is a chronic inflammatory skin disorder characterized by recurrent nodules, sinus tracts and abscesses, commonly affecting the axillary, inguinal and anogenital regions [11]. The pathogenesis of both CD and HS remains unclear. Some authors have shown that HS and CD may share certain risk factors (smoking) [12], genetic loci, and immunopathogenic mechanisms, such as TNF- α secretion and neutrophil chemotaxis [13,14].

While luminal CD has been previously associated with HS in several reports [11], to our knowledge, this is the first case of vulvar CD associated with axillary HS, in the absence of luminal digestive involvement.

In a 2010 systematic review of 136 articles on vulvar CD, the course of the disease was highly variable, with a spontaneously favorable evolution in some cases, response to medical treatment in others, and the need for surgery in 17 cases [3].

The management of vulvar CD remains difficult in the absence of consensus and standardized protocols. The basis of management is medical and varies between:

local or systemic corticosteroids, antibiotics (metronidazole, tetracyclines), immunosuppressants (Azathioprine, methotrexate) alone or combo-therapy with anti-TNF alpha (Infliximab and adalimumab)[15,16]. In our case, given the presence of Verneuil's disease, we opted for treatment with Infliximab infused intravenously with Azathioprine to avoid any immunization. The use of anti-TNF alpha agents is now recommended when Verneuil's disease is associated with luminal Crohn's disease by the French Dermatology Society [17].

Conclusion

Vulvar Crohn's disease is a rare localization that can be misdiagnosed in the absence of gastrointestinal symptoms, delaying treatment. Its association with hidradenitis suppurativa is even more exceptional and more difficult to diagnose, as one is the differential diagnosis of the other. In the absence of clear recommendations on treatment, management is multidisciplinary, involving gastroenterologists, dermatologists and gynecologists.

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